

Flight Report

HALO-(AC)³ – 2022/03/20 – HALO research flight #07

Cold Air Outbreak 1 — Day 1

Objectives:

- Characterize atmospheric and surface conditions before a cold air outbreak (expected for the next day), with still mostly southerly wind, including a cirrus moving northward, extended Sc fields, and cloud-free areas
- Fly parallel to the MIZ, over homogeneous sea ice close to Greenland, then over the MIZ itself, and over open ocean.
- Look at cloud properties over the different surface types.
- Characterize surface reflection and emission properties in cloudless conditions.
- On the way to the main measurement area and back, we wanted to sample curtains providing vertical slices through warm air moving northward, that would not intrude into the Arctic.
- Test the coordination with Polar 5 and Polar 6 during their first research flights within this campaign.

HALO Crew:

Mission PI	Manfred Wendisch
HAMP	Lutz Hirsch
WALES	Manuel Gutleben
SMART/VELOX	Michael Schäfer
specMACS	Anna Weber
Dropsondes	Max Ringel
Camera	Sebastian Schmidt
Pilots	Marc Puskeiler Michael Grossrubatscher
Engineer	Thomas Leder

Flight times:

Take off	07:58 UTC
Touch down	16:44 UTC

Weather situation during the flight:

A high pressure ridge extends from northern Scandinavia towards Svalbard. On its western flank warm air is transported northward, but it is not reaching the Svalbard area. At the northern part of the ridge a closed high pressure system has evolved appearing in the surface pressure plots, which prevents the warm air from the south to intrude into the Arctic. It initiates weak transport of cold air southward. This situation characterizes a transition between the transport of warm air from the south typical for the days before, and the conversion into a situation with mostly meridional transport of cold air from North to the south that is expected to begin during the next days.

DWD Surface Analysis: 20 March 2022, 12 UTC

500 hPa Wind and Geopotential, 20 March 2022

08 UTC

12 UTC

16 UTC

850 hPa Wind and Geopotential, 20 March 2022

08 UTC

12 UTC

16 UTC

Sea Level Pressure and Wind, 20 March 2022

08 UTC

12 UTC

16 UTC

Overview of flight:

After take-off we had to take a small detour because of the restricted military area at the northern coast of Scandinavia. Then we crossed the warm and moist air with vertically thick clouds and went into the direction of the Greenland coast. There we observed closed sea ice including cracks. Clouds thinned on our way to Greenland over the sea ice sheet. Afterwards we performed longer tracks parallel to the MIZ over closed sea ice, the MIZ and open ocean with variable cloud conditions ranging from Sc, mid-level clouds, and even cloud-free areas. On our way back we crossed the warm/moist air close to the coast of Scandinavia a second time. Altogether we released 18 dropsondes.

HALO-(AC)³, RF07, 20.03.2022

Vertically Integrated Water Vapor Transport (IVT), 20 March 2022

08 UTC

12 UTC

16 UTC

Vertically Integrated Water Vapor (IWW), 20 March 2022

08 UTC

12 UTC

16 UTC

Cloud Cover and Sea Level Pressure, 20 March 2022

08 UTC

12 UTC

16 UTC

Cold Air Outbreak Index and Surface Winds, 20 March 2022

08 UTC

12 UTC

16 UTC

Instrument Status:

HALO	
BAHAMAS	
BACARDI	
HAMP Radar	
HAMP Radiometer	
WALES	
SMART	
VELOX	
specMACS	
Dropsondes	

Table 1: Instrument status as reported after the flight for all instruments on HALO.

Flight Logs (all times in UTC)

07:53 Taxi
07:58 Take off
08:08 some cirrus above, no low clouds
We are climbing
08:13 FL300
08:15 All the time cirrus above, a lot of haze below
08:23 HALO is above clouds, no further clouds above us
09:27 FL410, cirrus below nothing above
08:34 We fly to the direction of our planned track. We have the permission to drop sondes wherever we like within Norwegian airspace
08:43 No change, homogeneous cirrus below, nothing above
08:51 Cirrus top slightly increasing
08:54 **DS01**
08:54 We have reached our planned track, cirrus below, nothing above
08:57 Clear air turbulence
09:03 **DS02 → failed**
Nothing above, cirrus below
09:07 **DS03**
09:09 Cirrus below, nothing above
09:14 **DS04**
09:15 Clear sky above, cirrus below
09:26 **DS05**

No changes, no cirrus above, below homogeneous clouds, atop of the cloud there seems to be some thin aerosol layer

09:35 Precipitation at the surface

09:36 **DS06**

09:41 Cirrus 500 m below HALO flight altitude, almost okay. We have asked the pilots to climb as possible, they have that in mind

09:42 Polar 5 appears on Planet, including the flight plan and the markers

09:48 Clouds below get very thin, more inhomogeneous, nothing above flight level

10:14 First sea ice observed through the clouds, clouds quite thick with some holes

10:26 **WP1**, curve (procedure turn), we see Greenland

10:31 End of curve

10:33 Beautiful view of Greenland, almost no clouds, but kind of haze

10:42 no more clouds, different surfaces below, new ice, ice covered with snow, land covered with ice/snow, well distinguishable from VELOX data

10:47 homogeneous ice surface below

10:51 Cloud-free, homogenous sea ice below

10:59 Sc below

11:12 Huge ice flows, broken, below us, just very scattered clouds below

11:15 Leads in sea ice

- 11:17 WP2 begin curve, sea ice, cloud field with shadow
- 11:22 end curve
- 11:20 P5 takes off, P5 not on Planet
- 11:30 **DS07**
- 11:35 Sc below, haze, sea ice below is scattered → MIZ
- 11:38 **WP3** Begin curve
- 11:43 end curve
- 12:07 clouds in different heights, 95% cloud fraction, sea ice fraction quite4 high
- 12:40 Three planes in the area!

- 12:44 **WP4**, begin curve, homogeneous clouds below
- 12:50 end curve
- 12:54 Homogeneous clouds below, 3 km lower than flight altitude
- 13:10 **WP5** begin curve
- 13:15 end curve, homogeneous clouds below
- 13:25 **DS08**
- 13:27 homogeneous clouds below, nothing above
- 13:35 **DS09**
- 13:37 homogeneous clouds below, nothing above

- 13:46 **DS10**
- 13:37 less homogeneous clouds below, nothing above
- 13:49 **WP6** begin curve (no procedure turn, short curve)
- 13:59 Sc below
- 14:00 three planes close by

- 14:11 **DS11**
- 14:12 Sea ice with leads
- 14:12 **WP7** begin curve
- 14:17 End curve, nice Sc below
- 14:26 Three planes fly in the same direction

- 14:31 **DS12** (additional one, released spontaneously because we were allowed to do so)
- 14:33 Thin cirrus below, cirrus top at 8 km, we fly at 12 km
- 15:10 Not much change, cirrus below, cloud-free above flight level
- 15:12 Polar 5 and 6 on their way to LYR
- 15:16 **WP7** begin curve
- 15:22 End curve, nice Sc below
- 15:36 Climbing to FL430 because of increasing to altitude of Cirrus

- 15:39 FL430 reached
15:42 homogeneous cirrus below. Nothing above flight level
15:50 **DS13**
15:55 **DS14**
Homogeneous cirrus below
16:00 **DS15**
16:09 **DS16**
Cirrus becomes thinner
16:19 **DS17**
16:25 **DS18**
16:27 Start plus-minus 20° roll calibration for radar, we do it twice
Only little clouds below
16:34 Radar calibration finished
16:35 Roll clouds below
16:43 Turbulence, lenticularis clouds

- 17:07 Touch down
16:44 Landing

Thanks to the team!

In particular, the Pilots!

